

Actions to Mitigate Energy Poverty
in the Private Rented Sector

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1 INTRODUCTION AND OVERALL METHODOLOGY

This document analyses and assesses existing policies in the private rented sector (PRS) across the EU and beyond. We review successful – and unsuccessful – intervention strategies aimed at advancing measures to address energy poverty among vulnerable households living in private rented properties. Our overarching objective is to investigate the aims, content and structure of PRS policies in this domain, while highlighting any key patterns in the coverage and distribution of such initiatives. As a result, the review identifies some of the wider structural challenges in the type of support currently available to energy poor households.

The analysis does not aim to be comprehensive or exhaustive; rather its objective is to provide indicative insights into the overall typology of support measures and interventions. Given that a global review with a similar conceptual remit has not been undertaken to date, this document proposes a framing to help develop methodological tools and analytical approaches for future investigations in the domain. Policies have been identified on the basis of publicly available, non-confidential and non-personal information. Data was collected by experts from the ENPOR consortium. Given the rarity of PRS-targeted initiatives, we did not use any special criteria in the selection of measures, other than containing some form of specialized support aimed at PRS tenants. This resulted in the collection of a diverse set of measures operating at different governance scales, and with highly variegated programmatic objectives.

The report consists of three sections. First, we review and discuss the measures that we have collected, based on a number of criteria, including who is implementing the policy, who the policy is targeted at, geographical and temporal scopes, whether vulnerable tenants are included, and whether some forms of public participation are involved in the decision-making process. We then provide an analytical summary of the policies based on well-established energy justice principles, followed by a conclusion with recommendations identifying gaps in present knowledge and practice, and suggestions for areas of further work.

2 OVERVIEW OF POLICIES SURVEYED

2.1 General description of the policies

In total, 35 policies from across the world were collected for analysis. The policies and measures collected by experts from the ENPOR consortium are listed in Table X, together with an embedded source hyperlink, active years of the policy and the operative country or region. Each policy is also given an acronym by which it is further referred to in this analysis for brevity.

Table 1. List of Policies Surveyed and Acronyms

Policy Acronym	Policy Full Name	Operating Country	Years Active
VSC	1. Verbund-Stromhilfefonds der Caritas	Austria	2009-present
G-EN	2. Gratis Energiescan Extra Info	Belgium	2007-present
STEP	3. Energy Performance Incentive Scheme for the Rental Sector (STEP)	Netherlands	2014
SI-Rental	4. Grants for Social Insulation Projects in Rental Buildings	Belgium	2016-present
WU-NZ	5. Warm Up New Zealand	New Zealand	2016-2018
NEST	6. Nyth Nest Scheme (Making Wales Cosy) Extra Info	United Kingdom	2011-present
ELoan-BE	7. Energy Loan Belgium	Belgium	2006-present
EBox-NL	8. Energy Box	Netherlands	2014-present
WAP	9. Weatherisation Assistance Programme	USA	1976-present
AW-Brighton	10. Affordable Warmth: A Fuel Poverty Strategy for Residents of Brighton and Hove	United Kingdom	2002-2010
MEBAR-II	11. MEBAR II Extra Info	Belgium	1999-present
SFHP	12. Solidarity Funds for Housing Programme	France	1984-present
WH-Scot	13. Warmer Homes Scotland Extra Info	Scotland	2015-present
PSRS	14. Private Sector Renewal Strategy: Better Homes in the PRS	United Kingdom	2008-2013
En-Consult	15. Energy Consultations for Low Income Households Extra Info	Austria	2011-2014
MPE	16. Mediation Précarité Energétique (Energy Poverty Mediation) Extra Info	France	2015-2018 (extended)

EAPs	17. Punts d'Assessorament Energetic (Energy Advice Points)	Spain	2017-present
Solar Savers	18. Solar Savers Adelaide Programme	Australia	2016-2018
HH-NZ	19. Healthy Homes Guarantee Act 2017 Extra Info	New Zealand	2017-present
ECO UK	20. Energy Company Obligation (Affordable Warmth Scheme) Extra Info	United Kingdom	2018-2022 (earlier iterations of scheme in operation prior to 2018)
GH Grant	21. Green Homes Grant	United Kingdom	2020-2022
WH Discount	22. Warm Homes Discount Scheme	United Kingdom	2020-2021
WHHP	23. Warm Homes, Healthy People	United Kingdom	2012-present
PRS LL	24. PRS Landlord Loan	United Kingdom	Ongoing
South Tees AWP	25. South Tees Affordable Warmth Partnership	United Kingdom	2020-2022
AWS - NI	26. Affordable Warmth Scheme Northern Ireland	(Northern Ireland) - United Kingdom	2014-present
Stockton Switch	27. Stockton Big Community Switch	United Kingdom	Ongoing
HEEG	28. Home Energy Efficiency Grants Ireland Extra Info	Ireland	Ongoing
Sérénité	29. Habiter Mieux Sérénité (Live Better Serenity)	France	2017-present
MaPrimeRenov	30. MaPrimeRenov Extra Info	France	2020-present (new scheme replacing an earlier iteration)
Smart Heating	31. Smart Heating Controls and Behaviour Change in PRS	United Kingdom	2017
SCP	32. Strategy to Combat Energy Poverty	Ireland	2016-2019
LEAP	33. Cosy Devon Energy Advice Partnership (LEAP) Extra Info	United Kingdom	Ongoing
Smart Regs	34. Smart Regs	USA	2011-present
PRS EER	35. PRS Energy Efficiency Regulations Extra Info	United Kingdom	Ongoing

2.2 Temporal and Spatial Extent of Policies

The policies and measures collected are dominated by policies and measures from Anglophone countries, with some French, Flemish and German language policies, and all are from Western European, North American and Australian contexts.

The majority of the policies were implemented at a national scale, a quarter were locally targeted, and one fifth were regional. None of the policies analysed here had a supranational coverage (for example, at the EU level).

Table 2: Number of policies analysed per country

Country	# Policies
Australia	1
Austria	2
Belgium	4
France	4
Ireland	2
Netherlands	2
New Zealand	2
Spain	1
UK and NI	15
USA	2

Figure 1: Spatial Coverage of the Policies

The temporal extent of the policies varied, with the earliest implemented policy recorded starting in 1976, and the newest in 2020. Though five measures were not dated, there was a bias towards policies implemented since 2010 (22 out of 30 dated policies), likely due to information being more readily available online for more recent programmes. 22 were ongoing or still in progress, while the eight remaining projects all ended after 2010. Of the projects with a finite duration, the average implementation length was three years, and of the ongoing projects, the average time that the policy had been in place was 11 years. It is worth noting that some of these projects, for example Sérénité, are iterations and improvements upon earlier policies and thus some of more recent policies have been in place for longer than the analysis accounts for.

2.3 Implementing authorities

Implementing authorities were diverse and varied. For example, some policies and initiatives were delivered by NGOs or local community organisations, such as VSC, by Caritas, an international, non-profit NGO linked to the Catholic church, delivering social aid programmes. Other programmes were initiatives by private companies, such as the G-EN, whereby the energy scans were carried out at the expense of the grid network operator Fluvius. Some measures are imposed on private companies by national governments, for example, the UK government ECO programme, which mandates that large gas and electric

providers with over 150,000 customers must provide eligible households with free insulation.

Nevertheless, **the large majority of implementing authorities were government bodies, albeit across different jurisdictional scales.** Some were local borough or city councils, such as Barcelona City Council and Stockton Borough Councils, to regional authorities, including the Walloon and Flanders governments, while the largest were implemented by national government departments, such as the French National Housing Agency (ANAH), and the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI). Many of these authorities further partnered with NGOs and local organisations to deliver the policy, or subcontracted local suppliers and providers to implement the works in the case of retrofits and installations.

2.4 Types of tenants and landlords included:

Perhaps unsurprisingly, as a result of a general lack of engagement with energy and fuel poverty in the private rented sector, **many of the collected policies were not directly targeted at the PRS.** Indeed, 66% of policies were general, inclusive of PRS tenants, homeowners, landlords and social renters alike. **Of the twelve policies that were specific to the PRS, ten were engaging only landlords or landlords and tenants, and only two were aimed only at tenants.**

Across all the policies, just under half (48%) were aimed at low-income groups, for example, household income being lower than a predefined amount, were conditional on being in receipt of certain government benefits, or falling within categories of vulnerability, such as disability. For example, the G-EN is available to renters who pay under €521.69/month or are eligible for the social electricity and gas tariffs in Belgium, while the WH-Scot scheme offers support to those living in homes with an energy rating lower than 67, as well as meeting particular social criteria, such as receiving the Carers' allowance or being over 75/pregnant and in receipt of benefits.

2.5 Technical and financial measures involved:

The measures and policies assessed demonstrated a diverse range of technical and financial aspects designed to assist both tenants and landlords, and some level of innovation and originality in tackling energy poverty was seen. **63% of policies included both technical and financial measures, with policies only tackling either finance or technical representing 17% and 14% of the policies respectively.** Only two policies were not categorised as involving either measure, but instead classed as primarily educational.

Technical measures were often aimed at increasing the energy efficiency of a household. These most commonly were through the implementation of large-scale loft, underfloor, cavity wall insulation improvements, indoor ventilation, installation of windows and doors, and central heating, and were often tied to the financial measures detailed below. Smaller technical measures included more energy efficient lighting, replacement of inefficient household appliances and draught excluders.

Financial measures ranged from advice and one-off payments, to subsidies and long-term loans for the implementation of technical measures. Most financial measures, as stated

above were available for financing technical measures. For example, GH Grant UK offers landlords in the PRS a voucher to cover up to 2/3 of the costs of eligible improvements – in this case, a ‘primary measure’ of solid wall/cavity/loft insulation or low carbon heating systems, and some ‘secondary measures’ if there is money remaining for thermostats, draught proofing etc – to a maximum of £5000.

WHDS in the UK offered a £140 reduction on electricity bills for the winter of 2020-21 as a one-off payment financial measure to alleviate low-income tenants’ inability to pay their bills. Although offering short term financial relief, this form of scheme does not offer vulnerable tenants any longer-term support for dealing with energy bills, or create any structural or regulatory changes to prevent the need for these types of one-off payments. On the other end of the spectrum, EL-BE, in Flanders, Belgium, is a key example of the long-term loan policy, whereby zero-interest loans of up to €15,000 are offered to vulnerable ‘priority’ households over a period of 10 years to fund large-scale energy efficiency improvements. Although free support is available for applicants to determine which works to carry out, choosing contractors, prices etc, this form of financial measure does place the household under a long-term and large financial repayment burden. It is also unclear whether this loan is available to those with poor credit scores.

Some of the financial policies were tied to the level of technical measures implemented and the energy efficiency improvements achieved, in the form of bonuses and extra subsidies. For example, the Sérénité programme allows for tax deductions on property income if energy improvements are greater than 35%, whilst the HEEG project increases grants by €300 if three upgrades are completed within one retrofit application, to incentivise more ambitious energy efficiency upgrades. Although this form of recompense does incentivise higher efficiency and a greater reduction in energy bills and carbon emissions, it does rely on the project owner (the landlord, homeowner or tenant) having a certain amount of capital to invest to start with, regardless of the generosity of the subsidy, and thus could exclude lower-income household from benefitting from this form of financial measure.

Financial advice, such as the EAPs in Barcelona, Spain, was offered to households, including support for reducing energy costs and increasing efficiency, understanding bills and finding appropriate tariffs, as well as processing subsidy or social support applications. Advice on rights is also given to those at risk of disconnection and thus offers a form of empowerment for the public against energy companies who may be acting illegally.

The policies classed as ‘educational’ focussed on informing tenants on energy and energy saving techniques, rather than implementing a particular technical or financial measure.

For example, EBox-NL engaged households with a visit from an energy coach, who offers energy-saving tips, explanations on how to use low-energy devices and creates a report for the residents based on their discussions. Although EBox-NL does offer small energy-saving products such as draught excluders, this is primarily an advice service. The other policy, STAWP, tackles energy poverty education in two parts. Firstly, it brings together partners from across the South Tees region, to ensure that tangible action is being taken on energy poverty and affordable warmth. This includes training courses and workshops to teach keyworkers and frontline staff about energy poverty and how to make onward referrals to schemes and support mechanisms. The other prong is the organisation of community

events, to raise awareness on efficiency, health impacts of cold homes and information sharing on resources and grants available, particularly targeted at BAME groups and those with disabilities and dementia.

2.6 Forms of public participation

Across the board, 13 policies explicitly recorded some form public participation. Public consultations in the policy design stages were the most common engagement strategy, with nine policies recording this form of participation, such as the SmartRegs programme in Boulder, Colorado, USA. This mandated that by 2019, all new rental housing required proof of compliance with a basic energy efficiency standard, and involved several stakeholder consultations and community-based working groups to co-develop the regulations. In the USA WA, throughout the 40 year duration of the project, semi-regular public hearings have taken place from which comments were taken into account when creating and updating legislation. In the formulation of the AF-Brighton strategy, extensive consultations were undertaken with numerous local organisations involved in affordable warmth provision, including local MPs, tenant and landlord groups, utilities providers, government bodies and NGOs such as Age Concern (now Age UK).

Many of the programmes were largely top-down policies and measures, with little stated public participation or involvement, particularly in the delivery stages of the projects. An example of this is the PRS EER in the UK. Although is beneficial to PRS tenants, by ensuring that all rental properties must have at least an E-rated energy certificate, and that by law, the landlord must provide an energy certificate if requested, there is little onus on landlords to explain what an E-rating is, or what this entails with regards to efficiency or financial consequences and so on. Another example is the aforementioned one-off WHDS, whereby an apparently arbitrary sum is simply removed from the household energy bill, without any discrimination for size of household or energy efficiency. Thus, as these examples demonstrate, engagement with the public on the real-world outcomes and consequences is on the whole, limited and superficial.

On the other hand, however, some of the programmes did engage the public through education and information about energy poverty, tenant rights, empowerment and opportunities to improve the energy efficiency within homes and lower costs of household bills. As detailed above, the EAP Barcelona programme offers advice information about tenant rights with regards to disconnection, as well as engaging the public through citizen outreach workshops and activities on energy rights to ensure they are not illegally disconnected. Another innovative form of public participation emerged from the Mediation Prec. in Lille, France, whereby a trained technician carries out an energy diagnostic during home-visits to a rented property, followed by a mediated discussion between landlord and tenant. This ensures that each party can discuss their concerns and experiences, and allows both views to be listened to. This means that there is more likely to be informed and engaged discussion on energy use and poverty, and in turn, more likely positive outcomes from the project, with benefits for both tenant and landlord.

2.7 Recruitment mechanisms

A key recruitment mentioned by several policies was the **referral of vulnerable consumers**

via local councils, social welfare organisations, charities and citizens advice groups. For example, in the AWS-NI project, council staff identified households likely to be affected by fuel poverty, and arranged home visits to encourage residents to take part in the scheme. Other councils, such as in the Stockton Switch, used local media, press releases and their websites in order to recruit participants to the scheme. In the NEST scheme, a broader range of stakeholders is used to ensure messaging reaches those who might benefit, working in partnership with health boards, charities and community organisations across Wales, specifically employing Partnership Development Managers and publicity activities in areas with high deprivation.

Another form of recruitment, for example, in WU-NZ, was **through the “lead generation” and self-promotion of local service providers who are registered to deliver the energy efficiency and insulation services.** In many cases, such as the WAP in the USA, the onus is on the household or resident to find out about and self-refer to the service or contact their local service provider. In the MEBAR project, among others, the recruitment process appears time- and energy-consuming for the applicants. They must obtain landlord permission, contact the municipality, who checks the application for legal conditions and eligibility, and receive a home visit from a consultant before the works can be approved. In addition, in the MEBAR case, lessors must waive any rent increases for 30 months following the works, which although is beneficial to the tenants, may cause conflict and disinterest in giving permission for the works to go ahead.

2.8 Delivery mechanisms

As previously mentioned, many of the **implementing authorities utilise registered local providers and contractors to carry out the works**, in the case of installations and retrofits, as is the case for Solar Savers, GH-Grant, MaPrimeRenov and others. For those policies which are blanket regulations for improving the energy efficiency of properties (such as HH-NZ, PRS-EE etc), **the responsibility often is on the landlord for finding the funds and motivation to renovate their property** to the required standard, although there are long compliance time-frames before the laws come into force. Other overarching national policies are delegated to smaller local authorities or municipalities who deliver the programme, such as E-Box and E-Consult.

Other forms of delivery of the policies are through **networks and partnerships established by the projects**, such as in the STAWP, which brings together a range of local organisations, including housing associations, community and voluntary groups, businesses, healthcare providers and so on to deliver various aspects of the policy. This community-based and cross-sectoral forms of delivery provides an opportunity for public and private engagement with issues of energy poverty, and can lead to increased project beneficiaries of the policy, as more networks can be mobilised to reach target groups.

2.9 Evaluation mechanisms

Many of the programmes did not stipulate an evaluation mechanism, which is in part a result of many of the measures being currently in the delivery stages. Others which did report a form of evaluation did not provide large amounts of data or information on this aspect of their programmes or policies, or the evaluation document was not provided in

English.

One ended project with a **fully detailed evaluation** was En-Consult Austria, which provided energy advice and small energy saving aids to vulnerable families. This project aimed to monitor all data collected during their consultation process, to find out to what extent energy consultations are useful for reducing energy poverty. In order to ensure uniform evaluation of data across the board, only one implementing agency analysed all the data. **One of the largest issues found was access to the target group** and thus the suggestion of ‘placement agencies/communication nodes’ was carried forwards. Another finding was that **much of the advice given by consultants was already known by the vulnerable household**, and that the package of energy saving items was more useful for the recipient. Finally, it was found that **the cause of energy poverty is often not due to user behaviour**, but as a result of particular situations, including social problems, illness and unemployment. Thus, **the project evaluated that a single consultation is insufficient, and actions needed to improve energy poverty should be diversified.**

Annual reports are also utilised as evaluation mechanisms throughout the duration of projects. For example, NEST Wales also publishes annual reports on the progress of their programme. In 2019-20, 15,800 homes received advice, with 4500 of these receiving a home energy improvement package, with a modelled average bill saving of £282/year. In 2020-21, the scheme will explore whether householders with specific mental health conditions would benefit from the NEST scheme, and also to further support the private rented sector.

3 ANALYTICAL SUMMARY OF POLICIES

We now move to an overarching analysis of the policies identified above. The analysis is undertaken along four axes. These are based on the basic tenets of energy justice as it relates to energy poverty (Gillard *et al.* 2017; Walker and Day 2012). The first two dimensions include questions around the ‘provision of resources’ (Bouzarovski and Simcock 2017; Lacey-Barnacle 2020) in the distributional and spatial domain. Here, we judged the presence of energy poverty measures through energy efficiency investment, new financing models or social assistance as well as wider spatial justice elements such as infrastructure development. The second two axes query the initiatives’ ability to provide ‘access to justice’ (Jeretina and Uzelac 2014), combining procedure and recognition justice dimensions such as the improved public or political acceptance and awareness of the energy poverty challenge in addition to the development of effective engagement mechanisms to address energy poverty.

The four aspects were examined qualitatively and quantitatively. In order to analyse the policies/measures, a grading system was developed, with categories based on whether the policy addressed a particular dimension of social justice. Questions asked included:

- **Distributional justice dimensions:** did/does/can the policy/measure improve the energy efficiency of housing, and/or the financial situation of tenants/landlords?

- **Spatial justice dimensions:** did/does/can the policy/measure cumulatively reduce energy poverty in affected neighbourhoods, cities and countries?
- **Recognitional justice dimensions:** did/does/can the policy/measure improve the public or political recognition of vulnerable tenants in the private rented sector?
- **Procedural justice dimensions:** did/does/can the policy/measure improve the participation of tenants and landlords in the decision-making process, and/or help them gain access to relevant schemes, procedures etc. that can help reduce energy poverty?

Each policy was scored for each justice dimension, according to the following metric: **0**=not met; **1**=partly met; **2**=fully met. In grading the policies, we acknowledged that the power relationship between landlord and tenant is not equal, and thus the tenets of justice that are applied in this analysis do not necessarily have the same meaning or outcomes for the two different groups.

Results are presented in **Table 3**.

Policy Name	Distributional Justice	Spatial Justice	Recognitional Justice	Procedural Justice
VSC	1	0	0	1 (access)
G-EN	1	0	0	1 (access)
STEP	1	1	1	1 (access)
SI-Rental	1	1	0	0
WU-NZ	1	1	0	1 (access)
NEST	1	1	1	1 (access)
ELoan-BE	1	0	0	0
EBox-NL	1	0	0	0
WAP	1	1	1	1 (access and decision)
AW-Brighton	1	1	1	1 (decision and access)
MEBAR-II	1	1	0	0
SFHP	1	0	0	0
WH-Scot	2	1	1	0
PSRS	1	1	1	1 (access)

En-Consult	1	0	1	0
MPE	1	1	1	2 (decision and access for both landlord and tenant)
EAPs	1	0	0	1 (access)
Solar Savers	1	0	0	1 (decision)
HH-NZ	1	2	1	1 (decision - empowerment for tenants)
ECO UK	1	1	1	0
GH Grant	1	1	0	0
WH Discount	1	0	0	0
WHHP	1	0	1	0
PRS LL	1	1	0	1 (decision and access – landlords)
South Tees AWP	0	1	2	1 (decision and access)
AWS - NI	1	1	0	0
Stockton Switch	1	0	0	0
HEEG Ireland	1	1	0	0
Sérénité	1	0	0	0
MaPrimeRenov	2	1	0	0
Smart Heating	1	0	0	0
SCP	1	1	1	1 (decision)
LEAP	1	0	0	1 (access)
Smart Regs	1	1	1	1 (access and decision)
PRS EER	1	2	1	0

We subsequently analysed these categories in a summative way – along established principles of energy justice – by grouping the distributional and spatial criterion into a single category: ‘provision of resources’ (Bouzarovski and Simcock 2017; Lacey-Barnacle 2020); and combining the procedural and recognition dimensions into a further category: ‘access to justice’ (Jeretina and Uzelac 2014). The results of the analysis (Figure 2) indicate the general absence of policies that meet both sets of criteria, and the relatively high proportion of measures that are primarily orientated towards the provision of resources.

Figure 2: A summative appraisal of the analysed measures based on distributional and spatial ‘access to resources’ (x-axis), vs. procedural and recognitional ‘access to justice’ (y-axis).

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this document, we have outlined the results of a detailed analysis of 35 policies and measures aimed addressing the energy-related challenges faced by PRS tenants across EU and beyond. Our review is the first of its kind, reflecting the dearth of specialized PRS energy support measures, despite the widespread recognition that energy poverty is most pronounced in homes concentrated in privately rented housing (Bouzarovski 2018).

We note that our analysis is constrained to publicly available information and the knowledge of experts within the ENPOR project consortium, and operating under time and resource limits. Future comprehensive efforts aimed at identifying any PRS-directed elements within relevant policy interventions and programmes will need to be based on a wide range of stakeholders, involving extensive and comprehensive data collection, and including countries with a less established tradition of assisting private sector tenants and landlords.

Overall, we find that the surveyed initiatives are principally implemented by the state, and insufficiently directed at low-income tenants. Most of the policies involve technical and financial measures, with a more limited number involving behaviour change and energy conservation measures. An even more limited number of measures address the regulatory and political context of energy poverty in this housing stock, and, as a whole, the public participation and policy engagement dimension is inadequately represented. Involving tenants (and landlords) in the formulation, design and implementation of future

initiatives and interventions is, therefore, paramount.

In the report, we have also developed a framing that provides for an explicit consideration of the different energy justice dimensions as they relate to energy poverty policy in the PRS. Having established the existence of overlapping strands of evidence demonstrating that efforts to address the condition are uneven across countries, regions and initiatives, it can be surmised that this unevenness creates additional spatial inequalities on top of existing ones. Different forms of inequality are woven together into historically- and spatially-contingent assemblages (Buzar 2007; Harrison and Popke 2011), through which certain places, and the people who live in them, are at a greater risk of energy poverty.

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